

COMPARISON BETWEEN EFFECT OF LETROZOLE PLUS MISOPROSTOL AND MISOPROSTOL ALONE IN TERMINATING NON-VIABLE 1ST TRIMESTER PREGNANCIES

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Abstract

Objective: "To compare the frequency of success of Letrozole plus misoprostol versus misoprostol alone in terminating non-viable 1st trimester pregnancies".

Study design: *Study Design:* Randomized controlled trial

Study place and period: Study was carried out at Obstetrics and Gynecology Unit-I, Services Hospital, Lahore from 15 November 2024 till 15 May 2025

Methodology: Eighty eight women were enrolled and were randomly divided in two groups. In Group-A women were given Letrozole (2.5mg every 8 hours) + Misoprostol (800µg) and in Group-B women were given only Misoprostol (800µg). The women were visit in case of symptoms otherwise after 7 days. After 7 days, transvaginal ultrasound was done an. Surgical evacuation was done at any time during follow-up period if required. If no surgical evacuation will be necessary over the 7 days, success was labeled. Data as entered in proforma and analyzed in SPSS.

Results: The mean age of women was 30.25±6.90 years in combination group while 29.07±5.86 years in misoprostol group. In combination group, success was achieved in 38 (86.4%) women, while remaining 6 (13.6%) required surgical intervention. While in misoprostol group, success was achieved in 26 (59.1%) women, while remaining 18 (40.9%) women required surgical intervention. The difference was calculated to be significant (p-value = 0.004). Fewer side effects were also noted. Nausea and vomiting was observed in 4 (9.1%) vs. 7 (15.9%) women, abdominal pain in 7 (15.9%) vs. 13 (29.5%) women, diarrhea in 5 (11.4%) vs. 12 (27.3%) women and fever in 14 (31.8%) vs. 13 (29.5%) women. But the difference was insignificant (p-value >0.05).

Conclusion: The success of combination of letrozole and misoprostol is significantly better than misoprostol in terminating non-viable 1st trimester pregnancies.

INTRODUCTION

If there is no chance of a live birth, the pregnancy is considered nonviable.¹ Subtle clinical signs such vaginal bleeding or stomach discomfort may or may not be present in women. In 8-20% of clinically confirmed intrauterine pregnancies, ultrasonography confirms missed abortions.² Missed abortions have been treated using a variety of medicinal

and surgical techniques. Vacuum aspiration, dilatation, and curettage are surgical techniques. In these situations, certain medical techniques are typically favored since they are costly and need anesthesia.³ Prostaglandins are used in medicine, both by themselves and in conjunction with other medications.⁴ Prostaglandin E1 (misoprostol) is one of the prostaglandins that has drawn the most interest

because to its great safety and potential for out-of-women usage.^{3, 4} Misoprostol is especially helpful for underdeveloped nations.^{5, 6} A third-generation nonsteroidal competitive inhibitor of the aromatase enzyme system is letrozole. When paired with misoprostol, its antiestrogen activity has been demonstrated to be beneficial in the pretreatment of pregnancy termination⁷. According to some research, using aromatase inhibitors prior to misoprostol to induce medical abortion improves treatment effectiveness and reduces the need for surgery.⁷ Letrozole and misoprostol have been used in recent trials to induce abortion. This drug can help induce abortion by decreasing the corpus luteum's synthesis of estrogen⁸.

The purpose of this study is to compare the effectiveness of misoprostol alone versus letrozole with misoprostol in ending non-viable first-trimester pregnancies. Letrozole is more accessible and less expensive, making it suitable for usage in our clinical settings. Research has shown that the rates of complete abortions with a combination of letrozole and misoprostol are different from those using misoprostol alone. Thus, this study will allow us to produce local data on the effectiveness of the combination of letrozole and misoprostol for ending non-viable first-trimester pregnancies. Therefore, if it proves to be beneficial, we will apply it in a clinical context to improve the women's outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

After approval from ethical review committee, this randomized controlled trial was carried out Obstetrics and Gynecology Unit-I, Services Hospital, Lahore from 15 November 2024 till 15 May 2025. Sample size of 88 (44 in each group) women was predicted with 5% level of significance, 80% power of test and percentage of success with Letrozole+ Misoprostol and Misoprostol as 80%⁹ and 51.8%⁹ respectively. All the women who fulfilled following criteria were enrolled by using Non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion Criteria: Women aged 18-40 years presenting with 1st trimester non-viable pregnancy were enrolled. Non-Viable 1st trimester pregnancy was assessed as <12 weeks based on last menstrual cycle with an ultrasound

picture of an embryonic sac showing following ultrasound criteria:

- Crown-rump length of ≥ 7 mm and no heartbeat
- Mean sac diameter of ≥ 25 mm and no embryo.

Exclusion Criteria: Presence of fibroid or uterine anomalies, women with asthma, heart disease, renal failure, liver disease, malignancy and history of thromboembolism, coagulopathy, and any other medical conditions in which medical termination is contraindicated and history of allergy to misoprostol or letrozole were not included in the trial.

After enrolment, informed consent was taken from either woman or attendant (Husband/ Parents). Demographics including name, age, BMI, gestational age, parity, gravida were noted. Women were randomly divided in two groups with the help of lottery method. In Group-A women were given Letrozole along with Misoprostol and in Group-B women were given only Misoprostol. In Group-A (Letrozole + Misoprostol group) received Letrozole 2.5mg every 8 hours for three days followed by vaginal Miso 800mcg on 4th day which is the day of admission and in Group-B women were admitted to receive only Miso tablet of 800 mcg given as a per vaginal dose and can be repeated if required. All women were advised to take Paracetamol tablets in case of fever and chills, and one tablet of loperamide if they suffered from diarrhea. Ondansetron was suggested in the event of nausea and vomiting. All side effects were managed symptomatically. The women were advised to come to hospital in the case of severe vaginal bleeding (>2 pad changes within 1 hour), a fever of 39 °C or higher for more than 24 hours, severe abdominal pain, vomiting and diarrhea >3 times in 24 hours. A follow-up visit was arranged on day 7 during which a transvaginal ultrasound was performed. Women who not aborted till 7 days was considered failure to induce complete miscarriage and surgical evacuation was performed under general anesthesia. Surgical evacuation was performed at any time over the 7 days follow up period if there was heavy bleeding. If no surgical evacuation was necessary over the 7 days and complete abortion observed on transvaginal ultrasound, the

outcome of treatment was labeled as success. Treatment success and other variables like side effect including nausea & vomiting, abdominal pain, fever and diarrhea were noted on a pre designed proforma by the researcher.

Data entry and analysis was done with SPSS version 25. Quantitative variables like age, BMI, were presented with Mean±SD and qualitative variables like success were presented with frequency and percentage. Success was compared between groups with the help of Chi-Square test. Effect modifiers like Age, Parity, BMI, previous history of abortion were stratified to see the impact of these variables on final outcome. Post-stratification, Chi square test was applied to see the effect of effect modifiers on success. P-value <0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

In this trial, we enrolled total 88 women with non-viable pregnancies and were randomized in two equal groups. The mean age of women was 30.25±6.90 years in combination group while 29.07±5.86 years in misoprostol group. The mean BMI of women was 26.74±3.76 vs. 26.15±3.77 kg/m² respectively. The mean gestational age at the time of abortion was 9.55±1.41 vs. 9.80±1.58 weeks, respectively. In both groups, most of the women were gravida more than 1 (multigravida). Details of gravidity and parity are given in table below. In combination group, out of 44 females, 8 (18.2%) had previous history of abortion, while in misoprostol group, 6 (13.6%) women had previous history of abortion. Table-I

In combination group, success was achieved in 38 (86.4%) women, while remaining 6 (13.6%) required surgical intervention. While in misoprostol group, success was achieved in 26 (59.1%) women, while remaining 18 (40.9%) women required surgical intervention. The difference was calculated to be significant (p-value = 0.004). Fewer side effects were also noted. Nausea and vomiting was observed in 4

(9.1%) vs. 7 (15.9%) women, abdominal pain in 7 (15.9%) vs. 13 (29.5%) women, diarrhea in 5 (11.4%) vs. 12 (27.3%) women and fever in 14 (31.8%) vs. 13 (29.5%) women. But the difference was insignificant (p-value >0.05). Table-II

Data was controlled for effects modifiers including age, gestational age BMI of women and gravidity. It has been observed that combination had significantly better success rate in young females (85.7%) as compared to misoprostol alone (54.2%, p<0.05). But in women above 30 years old, the success of combination was although better but found to be insignificant (C: 87% vs. M: 65%, p>0.05). Similarly, the success of combination was significantly better when given in gestational age 7-9 weeks (90.9%) than misoprostol (60%, p=0.025). But in women who aborted at 10-12 weeks, combination drug although performed better but difference was insignificant (81.8% vs. 58.6%, p=0.077). Combination group also showed better performance in women with normal BMI than misoprostol alone (16 (88.9%) vs. 9 (47.4%), p-value = 0.007), as well as in overweight women (12 (80.0%) vs. 8 (57.1%), p-value = 0.184). But in obese women, the success was almost similar in both groups (10 (90.9%) vs. 9 (81.8%), p-value = 0.534). Among primigravida, success of combination was 100% while success of misoprostol was less than 50% in primigravida women (p-value = 0.018). In multigravida women, success of combination was 83.8% while success of misoprostol was 62.2% in primigravida women and success rate was significantly better with combination of letrozole and misoprostol (p-value = 0.018). In women with previous history of abortion, the success of combination was almost similar in both groups (6 (75%) vs. 4 (57.1%), p-value = 0.855). But in women who did not have previous history of abortion, the success rate was significantly better in combination group than misoprostol alone (32 (88.9%) vs. 22 (59.5%), p-value = 0.004). Table-III

Table-I: Demographics of women randomized in both groups (n = 88)

	Letrozole plus misoprostol	Misoprostol alone
n	44	44
Age (years)	30.25±6.90	29.07±5.86
Height (m)	1.58±0.04	1.59±0.04

Weight (kg)	66.34±9.34	66.20±10.01
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.74±3.76	26.15±3.77
Gestational age (weeks)	9.55±1.41	9.80±1.58
Gravidity		
Primigravida	7 (15.9%)	7 (15.9%)
Gravida 2	25 (56.8%)	20 (45.5%)
Gravida 3	12 (27.3%)	17 (38.6%)
Parity		
Nulliparous	13 (29.5%)	10 (22.7%)
Primiparous	21 (47.7%)	22 (50%)
Multiparous	10 (22.7%)	12 (27.3%)
Previous history of abortion		
No	36 (81.8%)	37 (84.1%)
1 abortion	8 (18.2%)	6 (13.6%)
2 abortions	0 (0.0%)	1 (2.3%)

Table-II: Comparison of outcomes in both trial groups (n = 88)

	Letrozole plus misoprostol n = 44	Misoprostol alone n = 44	p-value
Success achieved	38 (86.4%)	26 (59.1%)	0.004
Nausea and vomiting	4 (9.1%)	7 (15.9%)	0.334
Abdominal pain	7 (15.9%)	13 (29.5%)	0.127
Diarrhea	5 (11.4%)	12 (27.3%)	0.059
Fever	14 (31.8%)	13 (29.5%)	0.817

Table-III: Comparison of both groups for success when controlled for effect modifiers (n = 88)

	Letrozole plus misoprostol	Misoprostol alone	p-value
Success achieved			
Age (years)			
Age 18-29 years	18 (85.7%)	13 (54.2%)	0.023
Age 30-40 years	20 (87.0%)	13 (65.0%)	0.089
Gestational age (weeks)			
7-9 weeks	20 (90.9%)	9 (60.0%)	0.025
10-12 weeks	18 (81.8%)	17 (58.6%)	0.077
BMI (kg/m ²)			
Normal BMI	16 (88.9%)	9 (47.4%)	0.007
Overweight	12 (80.0%)	8 (57.1%)	0.184
Obese	10 (90.9%)	9 (81.8%)	0.534
Gravida			
Primigravida	7 (100%)	3 (42.9%)	0.018
Multigravida	31 (83.8%)	23 (62.2%)	0.036
Previous history of abortion			
Yes	6 (75%)	4 (57.1%)	0.855
No	32 (88.9%)	22 (59.5%)	0.004

DISCUSSION

In this trial, success was achieved in 64 (72.7%) women, out of which 38 (86.4%) women were from combination group and 26 (59.1%) women who received misoprostol alone. In combination group, surgical intervention was

required in 6 (13.6%) women while in misoprostol group, 18 (40.9%) women required surgical intervention. The difference in the rate of success was significant (p-value = 0.004). We also observed few side effects during follow-up period. Nausea and vomiting were observed in 4

(9.1%) vs. 7 (15.9%) women, abdominal pain in 7 (15.9%) vs. 13 (29.5%) women, diarrhea in 5 (11.4%) vs. 12 (27.3%) women and fever in 14 (31.8%) vs. 13 (29.5%) women. But no significant difference was noted (p -value >0.05). Although first-trimester pregnancy termination techniques are common nowadays, the majority of these techniques are unavailable in most nations. Determining and detecting the optimal medication abortion regimen is therefore crucial. Further research is necessary to establish definitive conclusions, however some studies have suggested that misoprostol and letrozole reinforce each other's effects.¹⁰ Pourhoseini et al., revealed that misoprostol/letrozole had a considerably greater abortion rate than misoprostol/placebo (54.9% vs. 23.5%, p -value=0.001). In both therapy groups, no adverse effects were noted.⁸ Elbareg et al., When the effects of misoprostol plus letrozole were compared to those of misoprostol alone, it was found that the misoprostol plus letrozole group had a considerably greater complete miscarriage rate (80%) than the misoprostol group (51.8%, p -value <0.001). Additionally, there was no discernible difference in the groups' side effects (nausea and vomiting: 16.7% vs. 10.7%, stomach pain: 10% vs. 7.1%, diarrhea: 5% vs. 3.6%, and fever: 8.30% vs. 7.1%).⁹

Contrary to these findings, Allameh et al., carried out a comparable study and showed that, for first-trimester missed abortions, misoprostol alone was just as successful as misoprostol + letrozole (80% vs. 75%, p -value=0.80). There was no discernible difference between the groups in terms of side effects such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, fever, and chills. For example, nausea = misoprostol = 75% vs. misoprostol + letrozole = 70%, p -value = 0.54 Vomiting = Misoprostol: 26.7% vs. Misoprostol + Letrozole: 21.7%, p -value = 0.52 Diarrhea = Misoprostol: 15% against Misoprostol + Letrozole: 15%, Misoprostol plus Letrozole: 21.7% vs. Fever = Misoprostol: 16.7%, p -value = 0.49.¹¹

Misoprostol, a prostaglandin analog used to induce abortion, is a reasonably safe and reasonably priced option. Conversely, letrozole is a non-steroidal third-generation aromatase inhibitor that is excreted in the urine and has an average half-life of around 45 hours. Headache,

dizziness, and edema are possible side effects. It is not recommended to use letrozole when pregnant or nursing. By reducing the corpus luteum's synthesis of estrogen, this drug can help induce abortion.¹¹⁻¹³ Researchers examined the use of mifepristone in conjunction with misoprostol with a misoprostol-alone regimen for abortion in a pilot randomized double-blind experiment by Jain et al. They came to the conclusion that mifepristone + misoprostol had significantly higher complete abortion success rates than misoprostol alone.¹⁴

In a 2011 study, Lee et al. investigated the use of letrozole for second-trimester abortions in conjunction with mifepristone or misoprostol.¹⁵ The results indicated that both groups had a similar rate of abortion at 24 and 48 hours, which is in contrast to our findings. Yeung et al., and Naghshineh et al., conducted research that revealed supporting results.^{16, 17} Furthermore, a pilot study by Lee et al. investigated the use of letrozole in conjunction with mifepristone or misoprostol for up to 63 days of pregnancy termination. Their results showed that while letrozole combined with misoprostol may be beneficial for abortion, its combination with mifepristone is less successful and requires more time, which exactly mirrored our findings.¹⁸

Ali et al., conducted an experiment in Egypt and found that letrozole had shorter induction-to-expulsion and bleeding-onset durations ($p < 0.001$) and required considerably less misoprostol. 68.6% of controls had a complete abortion, compared to 42.8% of controls ($p = 0.02$). Letrozole caused less side symptoms, such as nausea, diarrhea, and cold. Researchers find that pretreatment with letrozole reduces induction time and side effects while improving the effectiveness and tolerance of misoprostol for medical termination of second trimester missed miscarriages.¹⁹

Abbasalizadeh et al., They out a comparable experiment for the termination of non-viable first trimester pregnancies and found that the combination group had a considerably greater complete abortion rate (93.7%) than the control group (68.7%; $p = 0.001$). Additionally, the intervention group experienced considerably less abdominal discomfort than the misoprostol group ($p = 0.013$). Additionally, the combination group's bleeding duration was

substantially shorter than that of the misoprostol alone group ($p = 0.006$).¹⁰ Srimahachota et al., Additionally, in women diagnosed with early pregnancy loss at a gestational age of 14 weeks or less, letrozole followed by misoprostol and misoprostol alone were compared, and the side effects of both regimens were assessed. They discovered that complete abortion happened in 65.7% of instances in the combo group as opposed to 62.9% in the misoprostol group. The two groups did not vary significantly, according to this (p -value=0.803). Clinical side effects, such as nausea and vomiting, diarrhea, headache, dizziness, stomach discomfort, fever, and chills, did not differ significantly either. They came to the conclusion that the rate of complete abortions for first-trimester pregnancy termination is not increased by the combination of letrozole and misoprostol. Furthermore, there is no discernible reduction in the negative consequences.²⁰

Regarding the impact of using letrozole and misoprostol to induce abortions outside of the first trimester of pregnancy, a clinical trial on the effect of using letrozole and misoprostol to induce abortions in the second trimester of pregnancy found that prescribing letrozole before misoprostol did not significantly alter the success rate of inducing medical abortions in the second trimester of pregnancy. Additionally, there was no discernible difference in side effects between the two groups in this trial. Similar to the previous study, a number of investigations have shown that administering letrozole before misoprostol increases the success rate of full medication abortions without raising adverse effects.^{21, 22}

During the study, we found that it can be helpful to prepare letrozole 72 hours before to misoprostol for normal pregnancy termination. This combination reduces the induction-to-expulsion period and greatly increases effectiveness. This trial's primary drawback was that it was a single-centered investigation, which limited how broadly the findings could be applied. Furthermore, extensive, multi-centered trials are needed to further investigate the optimal interval between the delivery of letrozole and misoprostol. To provide a more comprehensive assessment of this method,

future studies should focus on patient-reported outcomes, such as pain and satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

The success of combination of letrozole and misoprostol is significantly better than misoprostol in terminating non-viable 1st trimester pregnancies. Hence it is proven that combination can effect better than misoprostol alone. Now in future, we will incorporate the combination of letrozole with misoprostol to achieve complete abortion with least risk of side effects and need for surgical intervention in local clinical settings.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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